

Synthesis and Characterization of Copper(II)- Terephthalaldehyde bis-(Isonicotinic Acid Hydrazone)

BHAGWAT SINGH, P. L. MAURYA, B. V. AGARWALA and ARUN K. DEY*

Chemical Laboratories, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002

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Terephthalaldehyde bis-(isonicotinic acid hydrazone) formed by the condensation of terephthalaldehyde and isonicotinic acid hydrazone, yields polymeric complexes, $\text{CuL.X}_x.\text{xH}_2\text{O}$ [where $\text{L}=\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2$, $\text{X}=\text{CH}_3\text{COO}^-$ (a), Cl^- (b), Br^- (c), NO_3^- (d), $\frac{1}{2}\text{SO}_4^{2-}$ (e) and $x=1, 2$ or 3], which are coloured, powdery and insoluble in water and in common organic solvents. The composition, structure and polymeric nature of the complexes have been discussed by the results obtained from analytical, magnetic, spectral (Ir and Drs) and thermal studies. The order of thermal stability is: $\text{Cu(II)-a} > \text{Cu(II)-b} \sim \text{Cu(II)-c} > \text{Cu(II)-d} \sim \text{Cu(II)-e}$.

SCHIFF bases derived from terephthalaldehyde and carbazides are reported¹⁻⁵ to form several coordination polymers with various bivalent cations. Isonicotinic acid hydrazone well known⁶⁻⁸ for the formation of hydrazones of aldehydes and ketones, and metal complexes, has been employed to synthesize Schiff base with terephthalaldehyde. The isolated Schiff base, terephthalaldehyde bis-(isonicotinic acid hydrazone) (TBINH), has now been used to prepare polymeric complexes with copper(II).

Experimental

Materials: Terephthalaldehyde (Koch Light) and isonicotinic acid hydrazone (Wilson Lab.) were used to synthesize the Schiff base. Metal salts, $\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2.\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CuCl}_2.2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, CuBr_2 , $\text{CuSO}_4.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2.3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (BDH, AnalaR) were employed.

Preparation of Schiff base (TBINH): A mixture of 13.35 g (0.05 mol) isonicotinic acid hydrazone dissolved in 100 ml ethanol and an ethanolic solution of terephthalaldehyde (6.70 g, 0.025 mol in 50 ml ethanol) was refluxed on a water bath for 2 hr. A white crystalline solid precipitated, which was left for some time and filtered, washed with ethanol and ether, and dried. The yield was ~80%.

The compound was insoluble in water, ethanol, chloroform, benzene, acetone, toluene, xylene, but soluble in aqueous ammonia, and DMF. Found: C=64.61; H=4.23; N=22.35 and calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2$: C=65.51; H=4.33 and N=22.57%.

Preparation of metal-chelates: 0.01 mol solution of the Schiff base (dissolved in DMF) was added slowly to a solution of metal salts (0.01 mol) dissolved in DMF. Some metal salts which are not soluble in DMF, were first dissolved in a minimum quantity of water and then mixed with DMF. Precipitation was instantaneous, but the reaction

mixture was refluxed at ca 120° for 2 hr for completion of the reaction, and left overnight. The precipitated mass was filtered, washed with DMF, ethanol and ether, and dried.

The complexes are air stable and insoluble in water and in common organic solvents viz. ethanol, acetone, benzene, nitrobenzene, chloroform, methanol, DMF and DMSO.

Physico-Chemical measurements:

Elemental analyses: The metal-complexes were decomposed with fuming nitric acid and the metal content was determined chelometrically. C, H and N were determined by microanalytical methods.

Magnetic measurements: The magnetic susceptibility was measured using Mettler BE 22 balance at 25°. Copper(II) sulphate pentahydrate ($\chi_M = 5.92 \times 10^{-6}$ C.G.S. unit*) was used as a calibrant.

Infrared spectra: Ir spectra were recorded with Beckman Infrared Spectrophotometer^r using KBr pellets in the range of 4000-400 cm^{-1} .

Reflectance spectra: DRS were recorded on Carl Zeiss VSU-2P Spectrophotometer in the range of 220-1000 nm.

Thermogravimetry: TGA data were obtained from an assembly with a heating rate of 10° min^{-1} upto 800° in air.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data (Table 1) of the complexes agree with the general formula $\text{CuLX}_x.\text{xH}_2\text{O}$ [where $\text{X}=\text{Cl}^-$, Br^- , NO_3^- , CH_3COO^- , $\frac{1}{2}\text{SO}_4^{2-}$; $x=1, 2$ or 3 ; $\text{L}=\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2$].

The electronic configuration of Cu(II) having one unpaired electron in 3d subshell, warrants that its complexes should have magnetic moment close

* 1 C. G. S. unit = $\frac{10^6}{4\pi}$ in S. I. units.

TABLE 1—COLOUR AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Empirical formula	Colour	Elemental Analyses(%)			
		Metal found (calc.)	C found (calc.)	H found (calc.)	N found (calc.)
CuLAc ₂ .H ₂ O	Yellow	10.87 (11.08)	51.85 (52.18)	4.36 (4.18)	15.04 (14.64)
CuLCl ₂ .2H ₂ O	Yellow	11.53 (11.70)	44.32 (44.45)	3.53 (3.69)	15.26 (15.48)
CuLBr ₂ .2H ₂ O	Black	10.56 (10.35)	39.33 (39.12)	2.85 (2.98)	13.47 (13.69)
CuL(NO ₃) ₂ .H ₂ O	Brownish yellow	10.82 (10.99)	42.70 (42.47)	3.29 (3.12)	19.56 (19.39)
CuLSO ₄ .3H ₂ O	Red	10.26 (10.92)	40.08 (40.97)	4.10 (3.80)	14.51 (14.34)

L=C₂₀H₁₆N₄O₂; Ac=CH₃COO⁻.

to spin only value of 1.73 BM†, but in most of the complexes, the magnetic moment values are in the range of 1.75 to 2.20 BM^o. The observed magnetic moment values of the complexes lie in the range of 1.78-1.90 BM (Table 2).

TABLE 2—MAGNETIC MOMENT (BM) AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA (nm) OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex	Magnetic moment	Transition Band		
		² B _{1g} → ² A _{1g}	² B _{1g} → ² B _{2g}	² B _{1g} → ² E _g
Cu(II)-a	1.87	920	820	680
Cu(II)-b	1.78	940	670	540
Cu(II)-c	1.86	980	880	720
Cu(II)-d	1.90	1000	800	700
Cu(II)-e	1.82	900	780	700

a=acetato, b=chloro, c=bromo, d=nitrato and e=sulphato-complex.

The drs of the complexes (Table 2) show three *d-d* transition bands as shoulders due to Jahn-Teller effect, since the state ²E_g is susceptible to the distortion. The reflectance spectral values together with magnetic moment data suggest a distorted octahedral geometry¹⁰.

The ir spectrum (Table 3; wave numbers are in cm⁻¹) of TBINH shows the band at 3240 due to N-H stretching frequency. The carbonyl stretching frequency (amide I) occurs at 1640. A strong band observed at 1540 is assigned to amide II band which is due to a mixed vibration of N-H in plane bending and C-N stretching frequency^{11,12}. The strong absorption bands at 1290, 750 and 670 are assigned to amide III (N-H bending), amide IV (C=O in plane deformation) and amide VI (C=O out of plane deformation) bands respectively^{12,13}. The bands at 1630, 1490 and 1050 have been assigned to the stretching bands due to C=N, and nitrogen in pyridine ring, respectively. All these bands in the spectrum of ligands, indicate that TBINH is present in keto form and structure I proposed for the Schiff base is more appropriate.

I. TBINH

† 1 B. M. = 9.273 × 10⁻²⁴ m²A.

TABLE 3—INFRARED SPECTRA OF TBINH AND ITS COMPLEXES (cm⁻¹)

TBINH	Cu(II)-a	Cu(II)-b	Cu(II)-c	Cu(II)-d	Cu(II)-e	Assignment
...	3400	3420	3400	3400	3380	νOH
3240	3240	3230	3230	3225	3230	νNH
3050	3040	3040	3040	3040	3050	νOH
...	1665	1660	1665	1680	1660	δH ₂ O
1640	1590	1595	1590	1590	1580	νC=O
1630	1620	1615	1610	1615	1620	νC=N
1600	1600	1605	1600	1600	1605	νC=C
1535	1560	1560	1555	1560	1555	νC-N and δNH
1490	1490	1490	1490	1490	1490	ν-N= (ring)
1285	1300	1300	1300	1300	1300	δNH
1050	1050	1050	1050	1050	1048	ν-N= (ring)
915	945	940	940	930	930	νN-N
750	750	750	750	750	750	C=O in plane deformation
670	695	690	690	690	680	C=O out of plane deformation

In the spectra of the complexes, amide I band shifts to lower frequency, while amide II band and amide VI band shift to higher frequencies, but amide IV band remains unchanged. These changes in amide group vibrations indicate the coordination of keto oxygen to metal ion^{14,15}. The negative shift in C=N stretching and positive shift in N-N stretching frequencies suggest that the nitrogen of the azomethine group is coordinated to metal ion^{16,17}. The bands observed at 1490 and 1050 in TBINH remain unchanged which show that the ring nitrogens do not take part in coordination.

The presence of two bands at 1200 and 1025 in the sulphato complex assigned to stretching vibration of SO₄ indicate the coordination of sulphate group¹⁸. In acetato-complex, the bands at 1440 and 1340 assigned due to νCOO and δCH₃ respectively¹⁹, and in nitrato-complex, the bands at 1360 and 840 assigned to stretching frequency due to nitrate group²⁰, indicate that acetate and nitrate groups, take part in coordination.

The new bands observed in the spectra of the complexes in the regions 3420-3380 and 1680-1660 may be assigned to νOH and δH₂O, respectively²¹, and indicate the presence of coordinated water in the complexes^{22,23}.

Since the analytical data are reasonably in good agreement with a ligand to metal ratio of 1 : 1, and this ratio does not permit a monomeric complex to exist, as the four coordinating groups of one ligand molecule cannot coordinate to a single copper(II) ion due to steric factors. Therefore, two or more ligands are expected to coordinate to a single metal leading to the formation of a polymeric structure (II).

The percentage loss in weights on heating, at various temperatures (Fig. 1) indicate the gradual decomposition of the complexes. The abrupt change in weight shows the decomposition of the ligand. The order of thermal stability is : Cu(II)-a

II. $X = \text{CH}_3\text{COO}^-, \text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^-, \text{NO}_3^-, \frac{1}{2} \text{SO}_4^{2-}$

$(300^\circ) > \text{Cu(II)-b } (280^\circ) \sim \text{Cu(II)-c } (280^\circ) > \text{Cu(II)-d } (260^\circ) \sim \text{Cu(II)-e } (260^\circ)$.

Fig. 1. Thermal stability of Cu(II)-TBINH complexes.

The geometry of the ligand, and extreme insolubility of the complexes indicate their polymeric nature.

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References

1. M. MURCU and M. DIMA, *Rev. Roum. Chem.*, 1967, **12**, 1353; 1968, **13**, 359.
2. M. MURCU, M. DIMA and G. RUSU, *Rom. J. Chem.*, 1970, **52**, 349 (Cl. Co89), 05 Oct. 1970, Appl. 04 Apr. 1968, 2pp; *Chem. Abs.*, 1971, **74**, 126516u.
3. P. L. MAURYA, B. V. AGARWALA and A. K. DEY, *Polymer. Bull.*, 1979, **1**, 631.
4. P. L. MAURYA, B. V. AGARWALA and A. K. DEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 275.
5. B. SINGH, V. BANERJIE, B. V. AGARWALA and A. K. DEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 365.
6. R. C. AGGARWAL, L. PRASAD and N. K. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, **14A**, 181, 325.
7. A. P. NARIMANIDZE, A. M. MAMULASHVILI and T. K. DZHASHIASHVILI, *Tr. Gruz. Politekh. Inst.*, 1975, **4**, 34.
8. P. P. SINGH and S. A. KHAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, **14A**, 177.
9. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, *Advanced Inorganic Chemistry*, Wiley-Eastern, New Delhi, 1970.
10. I. M. PROCTER, B. J. HOTWAY and P. NICHOLLS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 1678.
11. R. D. S. FRASER and W. C. PRICH, *Nature*, 1950, **170**, 490.
12. T. MIYAZAWA, T. SHIMANOCHI and S. MIZUSHIMA, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1956, **24**, 408; 1958, **29**, 611.
13. T. MIYAZAWA, *J. Chem. Soc., Japan, Pure Chem. Sect.*, 1955, **76**, 341, 1018; 1956, **77**, 171.
14. G. D. PRASAD, D. N. SATHYANARAYAN and C. C. PATEL, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1972, **28A**, 2311.
15. M. NONOYAMA, S. TOMITA and K. YAMASAKI, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1975, **12**, 33.
16. P. A. GIGURE and I. D. LIU, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1952, **20**, 136.
17. D. NICHOLLS, M. ROWLEY and R. SWINDELLS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 950.
18. R. ESKENOZI, J. RASOVAN and R. LEVITUS, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 521.
19. K. NAKAMOTO, *Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds*, Wiley & Sons, New York, 1978.
20. C. C. ADDISON and B. M. GATEHOUSE, *Chem. and Ind.*, 1958, 464.
21. G. SARTOSI, C. FURLANI and A. DANIANI, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1958, **8**, 119.
22. F. A. MILLER and C. H. WILKINS, *Anal. Chem.*, 1952, **24**, 1253.
23. G. DEVOLE, M. MASSACERRI, G. PONTICELLI and G. PRETI, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 271.